

A GLOBAL/LOCAL MODEL FOR ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A global/local finite element model is proposed. The domain of the structure to be analyzed is divided into three areas: local region, global region and transition region. Three kinds of the elements are formulated by using combined energy variational principle. In the local region, the 3-D laminated element is used to accurately determine the ply stresses in composite structures near discontinuities. In the global region, the degenerated plate/shell element is used to model composite structure. Between the global region and local region, the transition elements are used to translate several 3-D elements to one 2-D plate/shell element and to guarantee the continuity and compatibility of displacement fields in different regions. An example is presented to illustrate the efficiency and accuracy of the global/local model.

INTRODUCTION

One of the difficulties in predicting failure in composite laminates is the ability to calculate accurately and effectively the stress components, particularly interlaminar stresses. Theoretically, it is possible to capture the structure of the stress field by considering each layer as a 3-D solid. However, since the composite laminae are very thin, the 3-D solid modelling usually results in poor accuracy because of the large aspect ratios of the 3-D elements. If the stress field is to be accurately resolved in a composite laminate with a uniform mesh of 3-D solid element, the mesh refinement might be beyond the capacity of the computers. The layer-wise modelling is a alternative to the 3-D solid element. The individual laminae are taken as 2-D layers. These layers are then assembled through the thickness. This type of modelling, however, is also computationally expensive. A typical composite may have many layers, each of which requires one 2-D layer through the thickness. The number of degrees of freedom per node is directly proportional to the number of layers in a laminate. This increases drastically the number of unknowns in a finite element model. Hence, these two models are both computationally prohibitive to model realistic structures. A resolution of the computational complexity arising from 3-D modelling of individual layers has been attempted by various plate theories. They usually lead to reasonable predictions of the overall response of composite structures, but they were insufficient in estimating the stress components, particularly interlaminar stresses.

In order to formulate an efficient and accurate numerical modelling for analysis of the composite structures, one possible way is to construct a global/local finite element model. A wide variety of global/local models have been proposed in the literature[1,2]. The main difficulty with these model (sequential global/local) is the maintenance of displacement continuity along boundaries separating incompatible subregions. In the sequential global/local model, the iterative methods are used to establish equilibrium along the global/local boundary. It requires

much computing time. In the simultaneous global/local model presented in this paper, special transition elements are used to connect two different subregions. The transition elements translates several 3-D elements to one 2-D plate/shell element. The domain of the structure to be analyzed is classified into three areas: local region, global region and transition region as shown in Fig. 1. In the local region, the 3-D solid element is used to accurately determine the ply stresses in composite structures near discontinuities. In the global region, the composite structure is modelled as an equivalent single-layer with the smeared laminate properties. The 2-D elements are used to keep the computer storage requirement down. Between the global region and local region, transition elements are used to translate several 3-D elements to one 2-D plate/shell element and to maintain the continuity and compatibility of displacement fields in different regions.

Figure 1 Global/Local Finite Element Model

For the analysis of composite structures, the main requirement in developing finite element is to satisfy all of the continuity conditions on displacements and transverse stresses at interlaminar surfaces and traction-free condition on the upper and lower surfaces. In general, the displacement elements can not satisfy all of these conditions exactly. The conventional hybrid elements usually contain six stress components and many stress parameters. Their matrix $[H]$ is very large. In order to overcome these difficulties, Huang and Hoa[4] proposed the combined energy and its variational principle to formulate partial hybrid element whose assumed stress field only contains three transverse stresses. It has been shown that the partial hybrid element based on the new variational principle can provide accurate transverse stresses and reduce computing time[5]. In the global/local model, the combined energy variational principle are used to formulate three types of elements used in three different regions.

A degenerated plate/shell element was developed for the global region[7]. It is an 8-node, 48 DOF equivalent single-layer element which is derived from a 3-D continuum equation by imposing one constraint on the 3-D isoparametric solid element: a straight line normal to the mid-surface before deformation remains straight but not normal after deformation. In the element, a partial stress field is assumed over the entire laminate thickness and it contains the stress modes with second-order terms to allow quadratic distribution of transverse stresses through the thickness of the laminated structure. It satisfies the traction-free condition on the upper and lower surface and the continuity of interlaminar stresses at interlaminar surface.

The 3-D elements for the local region have been proposed by Hoa, Huang and Han[4,6]. The elements were constructed by using the combined energy variational principle which was treated at lamina level. In this paper, these elements are extended to be treated at sublaminar level. The displacement field and partial stress field are assumed over the sublaminar thickness. Each sublaminar will be represented as an equivalent, single, homogeneous layer. This element also guarantees the transverse stress continuity at the interlaminar surface in the element.

The treatment of interfaces is one of the key elements in the global-local analysis. A new 3-D transition element was proposed[8]. It has three line nodes on the interface where it meets the

degenerated plate/shell element and twelve point nodes on the remaining boundaries. The line nodes can fit any function of degenerated plate/shell element along the thickness, meanwhile the point nodes have the same polynomial shape functions used for the 3-D element. The new transition element can be used to translate several 3-D elements to one plate/shell element smoothly over the thickness of plate and shell. The assumed stress field is constructed by the iso-function method and the classification method of the stress modes. The transition element has no zero energy mode.

GLOBAL/LOCAL MODEL

1. COMBINED ENERGY VARIATIONAL PRINCIPLE

For the laminates, the combined energy functional[4] can be expressed as

$$\Pi_g = \sum_{j=1}^N \int_{V_j} [C_j(\mathbf{q}) + \sigma_z \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} + \tau_{zy} \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right) + \tau_{zx} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)] dV - \int_{S_\sigma} T_i u_i dS \quad (1)$$

in which, N is the number of material layers, V_j is the domain of the j-th layer, S_σ is the boundary subjected to prescribed force, and \mathbf{q} is a global continuous vector, which is continuous through the thickness,

$$\mathbf{q} = [\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_g \boldsymbol{\sigma}_g]^T \quad (2)$$

$$C_j(\mathbf{q}) = 1/2 \mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{R}_j \mathbf{q} \quad (3)$$

the stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ can be divided into the in-plane and transverse parts,

$$\begin{aligned} \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_L\} &= [\sigma_x \ \sigma_y \ \tau_{xy}]^T & \text{and} & \quad \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_g\} = [\sigma_z \ \tau_{zy} \ \tau_{zx}]^T \\ \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_L\} &= [\varepsilon_x \ \varepsilon_y \ \gamma_{xy}]^T & \text{and} & \quad \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_L\} = [\varepsilon_z \ \gamma_{zy} \ \gamma_{zx}]^T \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

For the general anisotropic elastic material, the relation between global vector and local vector is

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_L \\ -\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_L \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R_1 & R_2 \\ R_2^T & R_3 \end{bmatrix}_j \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_g \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}_g \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_1^{-1} & -S_1^{-1} S_2 \\ -S_2^T S_1^{-1} & S_3 - S_2^T S_1^{-1} S_2 \end{bmatrix}_j \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_g \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}_g \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where R_i and S_i are modulus and compliance components respectively.

2. ELEMENT GEOMETRIC MATRIX AND STIFFNESS MATRIX

The element partial geometric matrix can be obtained as follows

$$\left[\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right] = [B_g] \{\delta\}^e \quad (6)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial w}{\partial z}, \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \right]^T = [B_L] \{\delta\}^e \quad (7)$$

and the element stiffness matrix can be calculated using following equations,

$$[K]_e = [K_d] + [K_h] \quad (8)$$

$$[K_h] = [G]^T [H]^{-1} [G] \quad (9)$$

$$[H] = \sum_{j=1}^N \int_{V_e} [P_g]_j^T [R_3]_j [P_g]_j dV \quad (10)$$

$$[G] = \sum_{j=1}^N \int_{V_e} [P_g]_j^T ([B_L] - [R_2]_j^T [B_g]) dV \quad (11)$$

$$[K_d] = \sum_{j=1}^N \int_{V_e} [B_g]_j^T [R_1]_j [B_g]_j dV \quad (12)$$

3. 2-D DEGENERATED PLATE/SHELL ELEMENT[8]

The co-ordinates of a point in the element can be written in the form specified by the 'vector' connecting the upper and lower points and the mid-surface co-ordinates as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{Bmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^8 N_i(\xi, \eta) \begin{Bmatrix} X_i \\ Y_i \\ Z_i \end{Bmatrix} + \sum_{i=1}^8 N_i(\xi, \eta) h_i \frac{\zeta}{2} \mathbf{V}_{3i} \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{V}_{3i} = \begin{Bmatrix} l_{3i} \\ m_{3i} \\ n_{3i} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{h_i} \begin{pmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} X_i \\ Y_i \\ Z_i \end{Bmatrix}_T - \begin{Bmatrix} X_i \\ Y_i \\ Z_i \end{Bmatrix}_B \end{pmatrix} \quad (14)$$

$$h_i = \sqrt{(X_{iT} - X_{iB})^2 + (Y_{iT} - Y_{iB})^2 + (Z_{iT} - Z_{iB})^2} \quad (15)$$

The displacement field is assumed as continuous through the entire laminate thickness. It is also assumed that a line that is straight and normal to the middle surface before deformation is still straight, but not necessarily 'normal' to the middle surface after deformation. The displacement throughout the element will be uniquely defined by the three Cartesian components of the mid-surface node displacement i , two rotations of the nodal vector \mathbf{V}_{3i} about orthogonal directions normal to it, and one transverse normal deformation in the thickness direction. The displacement field is

$$\begin{Bmatrix} U \\ V \\ W \end{Bmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^8 N_i \begin{Bmatrix} U_i \\ V_i \\ W_i \end{Bmatrix} + \zeta [\phi_i] \begin{Bmatrix} \psi_{xi} \\ \psi_{yi} \\ \psi_{zi} \end{Bmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^8 [N]_i \{\delta_i\} \quad (16)$$

where

$$[\phi_i] = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{11i} & \phi_{12i} & \phi_{13i} \\ \phi_{21i} & \phi_{22i} & \phi_{23i} \\ \phi_{31i} & \phi_{32i} & \phi_{33i} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{h_i}{2} [V_{1i} \quad -V_{2i} \quad V_{3i}] \quad (17)$$

$$[N]_i = \begin{bmatrix} N_i & 0 & 0 & N_i \zeta \phi_{11i} & N_i \zeta \phi_{12i} & N_i \zeta \phi_{13i} \\ 0 & N_i & 0 & N_i \zeta \phi_{21i} & N_i \zeta \phi_{22i} & N_i \zeta \phi_{23i} \\ 0 & 0 & N_i & N_i \zeta \phi_{31i} & N_i \zeta \phi_{32i} & N_i \zeta \phi_{33i} \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

$$\{\delta_i\} = [u_i \ v_i \ w_i \ \psi_{xi} \ \psi_{yi} \ \psi_{zi}]^T \quad (19)$$

in which, V_{1i} and V_{2i} are the unit vectors of the local co-ordinate (x' , y' , z') at node i . They can be calculated as follows:

$$V_{1i} = \begin{Bmatrix} l_{1i} \\ m_{1i} \\ n_{1i} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{\mathbf{j} \times V_{3i}}{|\mathbf{j} \times V_{3i}|} \quad V_{2i} = \begin{Bmatrix} l_{2i} \\ m_{2i} \\ n_{2i} \end{Bmatrix} = V_{3i} \times V_{1i} \quad (20)$$

If $\mathbf{i} \times V_{3i} = 0$, \mathbf{j} can be used instead of \mathbf{i} . The partial stress field is assumed independently as continuous functions along the laminate thickness.

$$\{\sigma_g\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_z \\ \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{zx} \end{Bmatrix} = [P_g] \{\beta\} = [T] [P] \{\beta\} \quad (21)$$

The matrix $[T]$ is assumed according to the traction conditions on the upper and lower surface of the laminates. For the analysis of the effect of free surface tractions, it is

$$[T] = \begin{bmatrix} 1-\zeta^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1-\zeta^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1-\zeta^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

The matrix P consists of a group of stress modes which can be derived from the assumed displacement field using the iso-function method. The stress modes are classified by the classification method of stress modes in order to minimize the number of stress modes in the assumed partial stress field which guarantees no zero energy mode. For the degenerated element, the matrix $[P]$ is assumed as

$$[P] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \xi & 0 & 0 & \eta & 0 & 0 & \xi\eta & 0 & 0 & \xi\zeta & 0 & \eta\zeta & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \xi & 0 & 0 & \eta & 0 & 0 & \xi\eta & 0 & 0 & \xi\zeta & 0 & 0 & \xi\eta\zeta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \xi & 0 & 0 & \eta & 0 & 0 & \xi\eta & 0 & 0 & 0 & \eta\zeta & 0 & \xi\eta\zeta \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

4. 3-D, 20-NODE LAMINATED ELEMENT

In the element, the global co-ordinates (x, y, z) of any point can be expressed to interpolate the co-ordinates (ξ, η, ζ) as follows,

$$x = \sum_{i=1}^{20} N_i x_i \quad y = \sum_{i=1}^{20} N_i y_i \quad z = \sum_{i=1}^{20} N_i z_i \quad (24)$$

where N_i is the shape function. The displacement field is assumed as continuous fields through the entire sublaminar thickness. The assumed displacement field is

$$u = \sum_{i=1}^{20} N_i u_i \quad v = \sum_{i=1}^{20} N_i v_i \quad w = \sum_{i=1}^{20} N_i w_i \quad (25)$$

The partial stress field is assumed independently as continuous functions along the sublaminar thickness.

$$\{\sigma_g\} = [P_g] \{\beta\} \quad (26)$$

The matrix $[P_g]$ is assumed as

$$[P_g] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \xi & 0 & 0 & \eta & 0 & 0 & \zeta & 0 & 0 & \xi\eta & 0 & 0 & \xi\zeta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \xi & 0 & 0 & \eta & 0 & 0 & \zeta & 0 & 0 & \xi\eta & 0 & 0 & \xi\zeta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \xi & 0 & 0 & \eta & 0 & 0 & \zeta & 0 & 0 & \xi\eta & 0 & 0 & \xi\zeta \\ & & & \eta\zeta & 0 & 0 & \xi\eta\zeta & 0 & 0 & & & & & & & & & \\ & & & 0 & \eta\zeta & 0 & 0 & \xi\eta\zeta & 0 & & & & & & & & & \\ & & & 0 & 0 & \eta\zeta & 0 & 0 & 0 & \xi\eta\zeta & & & & & & & & \end{bmatrix} \quad (27)$$

5. 15-NODE TRANSITION ELEMENT [7]

The co-ordinates of any point within the element can be expressed as in the form,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{Bmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^{12} N_i \begin{Bmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \\ z_i \end{Bmatrix} + \sum_{a,b,c} N_j \left(\begin{Bmatrix} x_j^0 \\ y_j^0 \\ z_j^0 \end{Bmatrix} + \frac{\gamma'}{2} h_j \mathbf{v}_{3j} \right) \quad (28)$$

In which, a, b, and c indicate line nodes. h_j is the length of the plate/shell element along the line node j. At the nodes $i = 1-12$, the N_i are the shape functions of the 3-D, 20-node element. At the nodes $i = a, b, \text{ and } c$, the shape functions are

$$\begin{aligned} N_a &= (1+\xi) (1+\eta) (\xi+\eta-1) / 4 \\ N_b &= (1+\xi) (1-\eta) / 2 \\ N_c &= (1+\xi) (1-\eta) (\xi-\eta-1) / 4 \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

and

$$\mathbf{v}_{3j} = \begin{Bmatrix} l_{3j} \\ m_{3j} \\ n_{3j} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{h_j} \left(\begin{Bmatrix} x_j \\ y_j \\ z_j \end{Bmatrix}_T - \begin{Bmatrix} x_j \\ y_j \\ z_j \end{Bmatrix}_B \right) \quad (30)$$

It can be seen that N_a , N_b and N_c are same as the shape functions used in the degenerated plate/shell element. The displacements field of the transition element are expressed as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{Bmatrix} = \sum_1^{12} N_i \begin{Bmatrix} u_i \\ v_i \\ w_i \end{Bmatrix} + \sum_{a,b}^c N_j \begin{Bmatrix} u_j^0 \\ v_j^0 \\ w_j^0 \end{Bmatrix} + \zeta' [\Phi_j] \begin{Bmatrix} \psi_{xj} \\ \psi_{yj} \\ \psi_{zj} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (31)$$

where V_{1j} , V_{2j} and V_{3j} are the unit vectors of the local co-ordinate at the line nodes. Along the boundaries separating subregions, the displacement compatibility is maintained between adjacent elements because N_i are compatible functions. The assumed partial stress field is the same as that in the 3-D, 20-node laminated element.

A NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

To demonstrate the efficiency and accuracy of the global/local model, an analysis of the free edge effect in a laminated strip with the [45/-45/-45/45] sequence is performed under uniaxial extension. The laminate has length of $2L$, width $2W$, and thickness $2H$. The thickness of each layer is denoted by h_0 and $W = 4H$. Each layer is idealized as a homogeneous orthotropic material with the following material coefficients in the principal material coordinate system:

$$\begin{aligned} E_L &= 20 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_T &= 2.1 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & (32) \\ G_{LT} &= G_{TT} = 0.85 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & \nu_{LT} &= \nu_{TT} = 0.21 \end{aligned}$$

By means of the symmetry of the problem, the finite element mesh used for analysis is shown in figure 2. Along the thickness of each layer, four 20-node elements are used near the free edge. In the central region, one 8-node degenerated element is used along the whole thickness of the laminate. At the boundary between two subregion, 8 transition elements are used to connect them. All elements have the same length ($=2L$). The width of the elements decreases as the free edge is approached. The result of interlaminar stress σ_z is shown in figure 3. The results calculated by the ANSYS Program and presented by Robbins [3] are also given. It only takes 62.09 seconds CPU time on VAX 6510 Computer to solve the problem by using the present global/local model. It takes 130.90 seconds CPU time on the same computer by using the ANSYS Program. For the analysis, the present global/local model uses 1154 active degree of freedom totally, ANSYS Program uses 1352 active degree of freedom, and the variable kinematic finite element model[3] uses 2354 (or 9116) active global degree of freedom.

Figure 2 Finite Element Mesh for Analysis

Figure 3 Interlaminar stress σ_z along interply face

CONCLUSION

It has been shown that the present global/local model takes less time and uses less active degrees of freedom than other models to solve the same problem and to get the same degree of accuracy. The proposed finite element model is a self-consistent global/local finite model in which all kinds of the elements are formulated by using same variational principle ---- combined energy variational principle. The model takes advantage of the capacity of both 3-D elements and 2-D elements. It can be used to model the overall response of composite structures having numerous layers, and predict local stress distribution such as the interlaminar stresses near the discontinuities of composite structures, with low requirement on computer storage size.

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